

FRACTURE MECHANICS OF MODE I DELAMINATION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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The delamination failure in laminate composites occurs in three steps : initiation, microcracking propagation, macroscopic delamination. These three steps may well be described in mode I delamination by the evolution of G , as determined by the compliance method, in function of the crack or microcrack length. Precisely, the logarithm of the increase of G over the initiation value G_i is linearly dependent of crack length with a transition point which defines the onset of macroscopic delamination. This analysis is presented for a number of composites materials based on glass, carbon or Kevlar fibers.

The total acoustic emission counts monitored during delamination experiments is also described by an exponential law in function of microcrack or crack length.

INTRODUCTION

Because the increasing use of composites materials in structural components, a good knowledge of the failure mechanism is necessary for a better design and an adequate safety. Among the multiple failure mode in composite materials, delamination is often encountered. Several loading situation induces interlaminar stress acting on the weak matrix layer. For instance tension on isotropic or $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates, or bending on thick beam produce failures by matrix or interface fracture. These mechanisms have been subjects of many papers [1] [2] [3] [4]. However the stress distribution in interlaminar layer is rather difficult to define in these studies and, as an example, the different method for measuring the shear strength τ_c , gives rather inconsistent results [5].

Considering the need of simplification for interlaminar failure experimental studies and according to the fact that defects are the failure initiation in real structure, we have designed a simple test of mode I delamination by pulling out the two edges of an interlaminar defect introduced in multilayered composite material (Fig. 1). This simple test was at first used in a study of the acoustic emission arising during delamination [6] [7]. This cleavage was already used by a few authors (F.J. McGARRY [8], G.R. SIDNEY [9]) for composites materials and also by people studying adhesion: MOSTOVOY and RIPLING [10] and CHANG [11]. Note that this cleavage experiment is simply the extension of the DCB sample used in LEFM study to an heterogeneous multilayered materials. Recently W.D. BASCOM used a tapered sample in which width is larger near the point of initiation in order to dispose of a "constant K_C " sample [12].

Fig. 1 : Mode I delamination or cleavage experiment

Our acoustic emission study carried out on glass fiber reinforced polyester, has shown the importance of the microcracking phase which precede the macroscopic delamination [6] [7]. Thus the interlaminar strength is not only characterized by an initiation fracture energy but also by propagation fracture energy which increase during the microcracking phase. The study, by fracture mechanics of this fracture energy evolution for a number of different composites materials is the subject of this paper.

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

The experimental load displacement curves (fig. 2) presents clearly the three phases of mechanical behaviour : a first part of elastic deformation of the two beams, a second part of slow growth of microcracks in the matrix layer and a third part where delamination crack opening occurs.

Fig. 2 : Cleavage experiment : load and counts rate in function of displacement

The amplitude of the second phase depends of the type of materials used. Also, in some experiments, depending of the defect length a_0 , the third phase, delamination, shows a saw tooth aspect, which indicates a stable-unstable propagation.

The mechanical analysis of this cleavage experiment has been well described by J.J. GILMAN [13] and J.P. BERRY [14]. The displacement δ may be simply expressed in function of length of defect a_0 , the load P and a material parameter h :

$$\delta = \frac{P a_0^n}{h} \tag{1}$$

Thus the compliance is :

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{a_0^n}{h} \tag{2}$$

$$\log C = n \log a_0 - \log h \tag{3}$$

The plots $\log C - \log a_0$ for experiments with different a_0 afford the coefficient n and h . The compliance method for determining G , the GRIFFITH fracture energy (here G_i for initiation) may be used :

$$G_i = \frac{P_i^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da_0} \quad \text{i for initiation} \tag{4}$$

$$G_i = \frac{n P_i \delta_i}{2 B a_0} \tag{5}$$

$$G_i = \frac{n}{2 B h^{1/n}} \left(P_i^{n+1} \delta_i^{n-1} \right)^{1/n} \tag{6}$$

B : width of specimen

During the propagation phase (phase 2 and 3) the equation (4) may be used :

$$G_p = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} \tag{7}$$

However, since some microcracking has altered the crack tip, the compliance is not known. Furthermore, for the non transparent materials, the crack length a is also not known. Thus we must, during experiment, reverse the displacement and determine at a few point of load displacement curve the elastic behaviour (fig. 3).

Fig. 3 : Determination of C_p with unloading during cleavage experiment

Knowing the compliance C_p for these points, an equivalent crack length a_p and a propagation fracture energy G_p may be calculated :

$$C_p = \Delta_p / P_p = \frac{a_p^n}{h} \quad (8)$$

$$G_p = \frac{n P_p \Delta_p}{2 B a_p} \quad (9)$$

$$G_p = \frac{n}{2 B h^{1/n}} \left(P_p^{n+1} \Delta_p^{n-1} \right)^{1/n} \text{ for the displacement } \delta_p \quad (10)$$

The calculated length a_p may be different from the real crack length a , because the crack tip is preceded by a microcracking zone. In the microcracking propagation phase, the macroscopic crack length is still a_0 , but there is a microcrack length a_m . In the macroscopic delamination phase, the delamination crack length is a_1 , and there also is a microcrack of length a_m (fig.4). Notice that a_p of Eq. (9) is lower than $a_0 + a_m$ or $a_0 + a_1 + a_m$. In transparent materials we may observe the length a_m in phase 2' or $a_1 + a_m$ if delamination has taken place. In order to use simple expression we shall use l_m for the observable damaged length or λl_m ($\lambda < 1$) for the equivalent damaged length in non transparent materials ($a_p = a_0 + \lambda l_m$). The variation of G_p in function of a_p is known as the resistance curves.

Fig. 4 : Length of damaged zone in microcracking and delamination phases

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples and materials

Mode I (or cleavage test) is applied to the laminates by pulling apart the two part of a partially delaminated composite (fig. 1). The artificial delamination is introduced during processing by insertion in the resin layer between two reinforcements (or between two preimpregnated layers) of a non adhesive thin film (paraffin for polyester, PET for Carbon and Kevlar laminates). Materials and samples dimensions are presented in table 1.

Fiber	Carbon		Kevlar	Glass Roving	
	T 300	T 300		270 g/m ²	830 g/m ²
Matrix	Epoxy		Epoxy	Polyester	
	N 5208	Brochier		Stratyl 166 RPI (S.116)	Norsodyne 294 T CDF (N 294 T)
Laminates	Unid.	Unid.	Unidirectionnal	Roving tissu 0 - 90°	
Volume fiber (%)	60	60	60	30	25
Number of layers (mm)	50	16	20	16	4
Thickness (mm)	5,3	2	2,1	3,2	3,2
Width (mm)	20	29,9	30	31	31,3

Table 1 : Samples and materials

Mechanical test and acoustic emission

The load displacement curves are determined on an Instron TTDM testing machine at displacement rate of 5 mm/min. Acoustic emission (A.E.) was used to monitor the stress waves emitted in the microscopic process of fracture. The signal of a piezo-electric transducer (300 KHz) is amplified, filtered and fed to a discriminator which transforms burst signal into counts (Leanord - CGR). The acoustic emission is recorded and may be used either as counts rate or as total count number.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initiation

Typical load and (A.E.) counts rate versus displacement curves are shown for Carbon-Epoxy (fig. 5) for Kevlar-Epoxy (fig. 6) and for Glass-Polyester (fig. 7).

Fig. 5 : Load and counts rate vs displacement, Carbon-Epoxy

Fig. 6 : Load and counts rate vs displacement, Kevlar-Epoxy

Fig. 7 : Load and counts rate vs displacement, Glass-Polyester

The initiation point A is easily defined from the A.E. counts rate although the load displacement curves does not show evident singularity. In table II are gathered parameters and results of the three sets of experiments : the n and h coefficients of the equation (2), the fracture energy G_i at initiation and its dispersion for the different samples in each set.

Composites	Carbon-Epoxy		Kevlar-Epoxy	Glass-Polyester	
	T 300 N 5208	T 300 Brochier		S. 116 ₂ 270 g/m ²	N 294 T 830 g/m ²
Number of samples	15	12	12	12	10
Range of a_0 (mm)	39 to 103	23 to 76	22 to 79	25 to 88	25 to 88,5
n	2,44	2,6	2,71	2,83	2,94
h (Nm ^{$n-1$})	20,4	1,356	0,59	0,43	0,321
G_i (J/m ²)	58,25	45,52	118,7	164,4	102,83
σ_{G_i} (J/m ²)	8,0	3,86	19,4	11	6,0

Table 2 : Compliance and G_i initiation results

According to linear elastic fracture mechanics, the G_i values for the different samples are independent of a_0 and dispersion is fairly low. This G_i value is a parameter characteristic of the resistance of matrix or interface to the first damage by microcracking. The measured fracture energy are of the order of 100 J/m² which are common measured value for pure resin. The Carbon-Epoxy composites is shown here to be the most sensitive to the initiation of microcracking in delamination.

Propagation

Behind the initiation point, microcracking occurs at the crack tip and the fracture energy G_p of propagation is greater than the initiation energy G_i . From C_p and Δ_p determined by a few unloading during experiment, G_p is calculated (equ. 10) for the propagation phase. These tests have been done only for a few samples. Since the increase of fracture energy arise from the microcracking phenomenon, it is interesting to look at the relationship between the increment of G , ΔG ($\Delta G = G_p - G_i$), and the length of damaged zone or the equivalent length of crack λl_m .

The three different composites, Carbon-Epoxy (fig. 8), Kevlar-Epoxy (fig. 9), Glass-Polyester (fig. 10), presents the same type of relationship, between ΔG and λl_m .

Fig. 8 : Increase of fracture energy, Carbon-Epoxy

Fig. 9 : Increase of fracture energy, Kevlar-Epoxy

Fig. 10 : Increase of fracture energy, Glass-Polyester

In a $\log \Delta G - \lambda_{lm}$ diagram there are two straight lines corresponding to two delamination zone. This type of variation is similar to the relationship between the logarithm of total counts number and λ_{lm} (or l_m) which was in a previous study the way we have detected the two phases, microcracking and macroscopic delamination [6].

Recently, on same type of laminates we have checked that transition at point B between the two phases occurs at the same equivalent length λ_{lm} in the A.E. experiment and the mechanical experiment. Thus the acoustic emission total counts is proved to be strictly associated with energy of fracture. Point B is indicated on the load displacement curves (fig. 5, 6, 7).

Since $\log \Delta G$ is linearly dependant of equivalent length of crack λ_{lm} , the R curves which describes the dependance of G_p in function of a_p ($a_p = a_0 + \lambda_{lm}$) must be composed of two exponential curves in the propagation phase, one for the microcracking and one for the macroscopic delamination. However the transition, cross point of these two curves is difficult to define in the arithmetic scale of the R curves. Thus this representation, although often used for large plastic or damaged zone is here not useful.

Some of the results of the propagation phase are presented in table 3. G_{pl} is the fracture energy at the point of macroscopic delamination, i.e. the end of pure microcracking (point B).

Composites	Carbon-Epoxy		Kevlar Epoxy	Glass Polyester		
	N 5208 T 300	T 300 Brochier		S 116 270g/m ²	N 294 830 g/m ²	T ₂
Length of defect a_0 (mm)	63	34	37	38	31	88,5
G_i initiation	56,88	48,33	98,9	160,4	109,65	94,8
G_{pl} délamination (B)	79,1	163,14	353,5	398	273,99	133,78
$\Delta G_1 = G_{pl} - G_i$	20,9	114,81	234,8	233,6	164,34	38,98
G_{pl}/G_i	1,39	3,37	3	2,5	2,498	1,41
λ_{lm} equivalent length of micro- cracks at delamination (B) (mm)	2	1	3	2,7	2,35	0,8

Table 3 : Microcrack propagation parameters

ΔG_1 represents the increase of fracture energy between initiation of microcracking and onset of macroscopic delamination. This value is thus a measurement of the extent of the microcracking phenomenon in these materials. For equivalent a_0 , ΔG_1 is clearly higher for Kevlar-Epoxy and Glass-Polyester than for Carbon-Epoxy. The same difference is found for λ_{lm} (1), the equivalent crack length at onset of delamination. The microcrack contribution to the very high toughness of these materials is here confirmed in a stress state which only strain the matrix. For instance, in cleaved unidirectional sample, such an extent of microcracking state the question of the origin of the multiple initiation points, heterogeneity or internal stress in the cured resin.

However ΔG_1 is dependant of length a_0 and thus is not a material constant. The evolution of G_{pl} in function of a_0 is presented in fig. 11 for one Glass-Polyester composites we have recently extensively studied. For small a_0 , G_{pl} is much higher.

Fig. 11 : Evolution of the fracture energy at the point of macroscopic delamination vs of length a_0 , Glass-Polyester

Then we must consider, since the onset of macroscopic delamination is a fracture of a damaged matrix between reinforcement layers, that the structure of the damages is dependant of a_0 . This hypothesis is consistent with the influence of a_0 on the slope of the curves $\log \Delta G$ vs λl_m in the microcracking phase. Differences of behaviour for different a_0 are summarized in table 4.

a_0	small	large
λl_m at onset of delamination	large	small
slope $\log \Delta G - \lambda l_m$	low	high
G_{pl}	high	low
density of microcracks at the tip of initial crack (hypothesis)	low	high

Table 4 : Influence of initial crack length a_0 on the propagation phase

Since the slope of the curves $\log \Sigma N$ in A.E. vs λl_m is not dependant of a_0 we may state the hypothesis that the rate of microcrack advent in terms of number is not a_0 dependant but the shape of microcrack is a_0 dependant. If this hypothesis hold, the density of microcrack and hence the fracture energy of microcracked zone is a_0 dependant. This description has to be verified by microfractography. Work are now under progress in order to get better correlation, for a set of sample with different a_0 , between acoustic emission and fracture energy during the propagation

phase.

CONCLUSION

In cleavage experiment, parallel to the reinforcement layers, the microcracking phenomenon has been characterized extensively :

The initiation fracture energy is a measure of matrix or interfacial strength at a microscopic level.

The growth of fracture energy during propagation is proved to be an exponential function of crack extension.

The point of macroscopic delamination is easily defined by the evolution of fracture energy.

This result confirms previous study with acoustic emission and opens new way to study relationship between A.E. and fracture energy.

REFERENCES

- 1 PIPES R.B. and PAGANO N.S., Journal Composite Materials, Vol. 4, 1970, pp. 538 - 548
- 2 PAGANO N.S. and PIPES R.B., Journal Composite Materials, Vol. 5, 1971, pp. 50 - 57
3. REIFSNIDER K.L., HENNEKE E.G. and STINCHCOMB W.W., ASTM.STP 617, 1977, pp. 93 - 105
4. RYBICKI E.F., SCHUESER D.W. and FOX J., Journal Composites Materials, Vol. 11, 1977, pp. 470- 481
5. CHIAO C.C., MOORE R.L. and CHIAO T.T., Composites, Vol. 8, July (1977) pp. 161 - 169
6. DE CHARENTENAY F.X., BETHMONT M., BENZEGGAGH M. and CHRETIEN J.F., ICM 3 Cambridge, England, Vol. 3, 1979, pp. 241 - 251
7. BETHMONT M., Thèse 3ème cycle, "Etude par émission acoustique de matériaux composites stratifiés", U.T. Compiègne, 13 Juin 1977
- 8 McKENNA G.B., MANDELL J.F. and McGARRY F.J., M.I.T., Research Report R 72-76, Dec. 1972, pp. 1 - 31
- 9 SIDEY G.R. and BRADSHAW F.J., International Conf. on Carbon Fibres, their composites and application, London 1971, Paper n° 25, pp. 1 - 6
- 10 RIPLING E.J., MOSTOVOY S. and PATRICK R.L., Mat. Res. & Standards, Vol. 4, 1964, pp. 129 - 134
- 11 CHANG D.J., MUKI R. and WESTMANN R.A., Int. Journal Solids Structures, Vol. 12, 1976, pp. 13 - 26
- 12 BASCOM W.D., BITNER J.L., MOULTON R.J. and SIEBERT A.R., Composites, Vol. 11, n° 1, Janv. 1980, pp. 9 - 18
13. GILMAN J.J., Journal of Applied Physics, Vol. 31, n° 12, Dec. 1960, pp. 2208 - 2218
14. BERRY J.L., Journal of Applied Physics, Vol. 34, 1963, pp. 62